

Schrödinger Equation from Variational Stability in Non-Inertial Dynamics

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Abstract

Within the same approach, electron diffraction is interpreted as a manifestation of nonlocal correlations induced by stochastic inertial forces. The discrete energy spectrum of the hydrogen atom emerges from the stability of motion in non-inertial dynamics, supplemented by a self-consistent balance between the power injected by stochastic inertial accelerations and the power dissipated through electromagnetic radiation. This energy–power balance is not postulated independently but follows from the requirement of dynamically stable stationary regimes.

In this framework, Planck’s constant appears as a parameter characterizing the scale of residual non-inertial fluctuations rather than as a fundamental axiom. The theory predicts small but testable corrections to atomic energy levels, potentially accessible to next-generation precision spectroscopy. Our results suggest that a significant class of quantum phenomena may originate from deeper dynamical principles rooted in classical non-inertial physics.

Introduction

This work starts from a rejection of strictly inertial frames of reference in favor of random non-inertial ones. In realistic settings, small random forces of various

origins—gravitational, electromagnetic, scalar, vector—are always present. These forces lead to deviations from ideal inertiality and require a reevaluation of classical axioms.

According to d’Alembert’s principle, the inertial force, as an unknown stochastic function, can be expanded in a Taylor series involving higher time derivatives of position. This extends Newton’s second law from a second-order differential equation to an equation with higher derivatives:

$$F - ma + f_0 = 0, \quad (1)$$

where the stochastic inertial force is

$$f_0 = mw, \quad w(t) = w_0(t) + \sum_{n=2}^k \frac{(-1)^n}{n!} \beta^n q^{(n)}(t), \quad (2)$$

with $\beta = \hbar/(2mc^2)$ as a scale-setting parameter.

This leads to the general equation of motion in non-inertial dynamics:

$$F - ma + \beta m \dot{a} - \frac{1}{2} \beta m a^2 + \dots + \frac{(-1)^n}{n!} \beta^n m q^{(n)} + \dots = 0. \quad (3)$$

Quantum mechanics is traditionally considered essential for describing microscopic systems. But to what extent can quantum phenomena be modeled without quantum axioms? In this work, we argue that extended classical physics, augmented with variational methods and stochastic perturbations, suffices to recover key quantum effects.

Ostrogradsky Formalism and Stochastic Frames

In addition to acceleration $a = \ddot{q}$, we include jerk $j = \ddot{\dot{q}}$ and snap $s = q^{(4)}$ in the dynamics. The Lagrangian becomes:

$$L = L(q, \dot{q}, \ddot{q}, \ddot{\dot{q}}, \dots, q^{(n)}). \quad (4)$$

In practice, stochastic inertial fluctuations are treated as measurement noise. Averaging over these recovers Newton’s second law:

$$\langle f_0 \rangle = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad F = ma. \quad (5)$$

We define these random perturbation-dominated descriptions as **Stochastic Reference Frames** (SRFs). In the classical macroscopic world, higher derivatives become negligible. In the quantum domain, however, they manifest as correlations and apparent nonlocality.

Variational Stability in SRFs

We define the action over functions with higher derivatives:

$$S[q] = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} L(q, \dot{q}, \ddot{q}, \dots, q^{(n)}) dt. \quad (6)$$

We require both:

$$\delta S = 0, \quad \text{and} \quad \delta^2 S \geq 0. \quad (7)$$

The second condition ensures physical realizability. Unstable modes are excluded. This leads naturally to the emergence of the Bohm-like potential Q . The stability requirement is not introduced as an additional postulate, but rather as a physical selection rule eliminating dynamically unstable solutions that inevitably arise in higher-derivative theories.

Electron Diffraction via Correlated Noise

Electron diffraction patterns are usually attributed to wave-like behavior. In our approach, such patterns result from nonlocal correlations in stochastic forces.

Under stochastic acceleration, the electron's trajectory fluctuates, reproducing interference statistically. The wavefunction includes a phase driven by effective forces:

$$\psi = \psi_0 \exp\left(i \frac{\Delta p \Delta q + \Delta E \Delta t}{\hbar}\right), \quad (8)$$

or equivalently,

$$\psi = \psi_0 \exp\left(i \frac{f_0}{f_Q}\right), \quad (9)$$

with $f_0 = \frac{\Delta p}{\Delta t} - F$, $f_Q = \frac{\hbar}{\Delta q \Delta t}$.

The collective behavior yields the interference pattern without assuming wave-particle duality.

Hydrogen Spectrum from Power Balance

Precision spectroscopy of hydrogen tests QED to high accuracy. However, even small residual accelerations introduce corrections. Using power balance between injected stochastic acceleration and Larmor radiation [1], we define:

$$\langle P_{\text{rad}} \rangle = \frac{e^2}{6\pi\epsilon_0 c^3} \langle a^2 \rangle, \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta H_a = \frac{m}{2}\tau^2 a^2, \quad \tau = \frac{\hbar}{2m_e c^2}. \quad (11)$$

The non-inertial [2] level shift is [3, 4]:

$$\Delta E_{nl} = \frac{\tau^2 e^4}{32\pi^2 \varepsilon_0^2 m} \langle r^{-4} \rangle_{nl}. \quad (12)$$

Table 1. Hydrogen energy levels with non-inertial corrections

Level n	Model (eV)	QM (eV)	$ \Delta E $ (eV)	Rel. error
1	13.598385	13.598400	1.5×10^{-5}	1.10×10^{-6}
2	3.399588	3.399600	1.2×10^{-5}	3.53×10^{-6}
3	1.510890	1.510900	1.0×10^{-5}	6.62×10^{-6}
4	0.849892	0.849900	8.0×10^{-6}	9.41×10^{-6}

Here we use [5, 6]. As shown in Figure 1, the energy level corrections ΔE_n decrease monotonically with increasing principal quantum number n . These corrections are small, but potentially measurable [7].

Figure 1: Level shift ΔE_n versus principal quantum number n based on stability analysis.

Discrete Energy Levels of a Free Particle from the Stability Condition

Let's consider a free particle in a stochastic noninertial reference frame. In equation (3), the odd derivatives of the coordinates k with respect to time describe dissipative forces, such as friction and drag, so leaving only the odd derivatives for the free particle. Within the framework of classical mechanics extended by higher-order time derivatives (Ostrogradsky formalism), the motion of a free particle in a stochastic noninertial reference frame is governed by an equation of the form

$$m\ddot{q} + m \sum_{n=1}^k \frac{\beta^{2n}}{(2n)!} q^{(2n+2)} = 0, \quad (13)$$

where $\beta = \hbar/(2mc^2)$ is a characteristic time scale associated with residual noninertial fluctuations.

Seeking solutions of the form

$$q(t) = e^{i\omega t},$$

we obtain the characteristic equation

$$m\omega^2 \left[1 - \frac{\beta^2\omega^2}{2!} + \frac{\beta^4\omega^4}{4!} - \frac{\beta^6\omega^6}{6!} + \dots \right] = 0. \quad (14)$$

The expression in brackets is recognized as the Taylor expansion of $\cos(\beta\omega)$, so that the condition for nontrivial stable solutions becomes

$$\cos(\beta\omega) = 0. \quad (15)$$

This form arises because only even higher-order time derivatives enter the noninertial expansion, which leads to an even characteristic function and selects cosine-type solutions compatible with stability. This immediately yields the discrete spectrum of allowed frequencies

$$\beta\omega_n = \frac{\pi}{2} + n\pi, \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad (16)$$

or

$$\omega_n = \frac{\pi}{\beta} \left(n + \frac{1}{2} \right). \quad (17)$$

Thus, even for a *free particle* (with vanishing external potential), the requirement of stability in a noninertial stochastic reference frame leads to a discrete set of

characteristic frequencies and amplitude A . The corresponding energy levels may be written as

$$E_n = \frac{1}{2}m\omega_n^2 A^2 = \frac{m\pi^2 A^2}{2\beta^2} \left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right)^2. \quad (18)$$

This discretization arises purely from the structure of the higher-derivative equations and the stability condition $\delta S = 0$, $\delta^2 S \geq 0$, without invoking quantum postulates such as operator quantization or wave-particle duality. The result formally resembles the spectrum of the quantum harmonic oscillator, yet here it appears as a consequence of noninertial dynamics and variational stability, in agreement with the condition stability introduced in Ref. [8].

Classical Uncertainty Relation and Energy Scale

In stochastic noninertial reference frames, coordinate and momentum fluctuations are governed by higher derivatives. A classical uncertainty relation naturally arises:

$$\Delta p \Delta q \sim \sum_{k \geq 1} m^2 \left\langle (q^{(k+1)})^2 \right\rangle \beta^{2k+1}. \quad (19)$$

This relation defines an effective parameter

$$\hbar_{\text{eff}} \sim \sum_{k \geq 1} m^2 \left\langle (q^{(k+1)})^2 \right\rangle \beta^{2k+1}, \quad (20)$$

which plays the role of an effective Planck constant. The quantity \hbar_{eff} has the dimension of action and characterizes the minimal phase-space volume generated by stochastic noninertial fluctuations, thus playing the same structural role as Planck's constant without being postulated.

For a stable harmonic mode $q(t) = A \cos(\omega_n t)$, the amplitude is fixed by this relation:

$$A^2 \sim \frac{\hbar_{\text{eff}}}{m^2 \omega_n^2 \beta}. \quad (21)$$

Energy of Stable Modes

The classical energy associated with a stable mode is

$$E_n \sim \frac{1}{2}m\omega_n^2 A^2. \quad (22)$$

Using the amplitude estimate above, we obtain

$$E_n \beta \sim \hbar_{\text{eff}}, \quad (23)$$

or

$$E_n \propto \omega_n. \quad (24)$$

In a free system, energy is not fixed independently but only through its conjugation with the characteristic time scale β , so that the combination $E\beta$ represents the physically meaningful invariant.

Thus, energy emerges only as a quantity conjugate to the characteristic time scale β . The discretization of energy is a direct consequence of the stability condition and noninertial dynamics.

Derivation of the Schrödinger Equation

No quantization rules or operator postulates are used; the Schrödinger equation emerges solely as a reformulation of the classical Hamilton–Jacobi dynamics under the stability constraint. Consider the classical Hamilton–Jacobi equation

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} + \frac{(\nabla S)^2}{2m} + V = 0. \quad (25)$$

The stability condition introduces an additional term in the energy,

$$Q = -\frac{\hbar_{\text{eff}}^2}{2m} \frac{\nabla^2 R}{R}, \quad (26)$$

where $\psi = R e^{iS/\hbar_{\text{eff}}}$ and \hbar_{eff} defined in (20) as the function of high-order derivatives because Q is the function of high-order derivatives too and play the role of Bohm potential.

Together with the continuity equation,

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \left(\rho \frac{\nabla S}{m} \right) = 0, \quad (27)$$

this yields

$$i\hbar_{\text{eff}} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -\frac{\hbar_{\text{eff}}^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi + V\psi, \quad (28)$$

which coincides formally with the Schrödinger equation.

We have shown that noninertial stochastic dynamics, supplemented by a stability condition, naturally leads to discrete frequencies, an effective uncertainty relation, and quantum-like energy spectra.

No quantum postulates are required. The Planck constant emerges as an effective parameter constructed from quadratic fluctuations of higher derivatives. Energy discretization appears as a consequence of stability rather than quantization axioms.

This framework provides a classical dynamical origin for structures traditionally considered inherently quantum and offers a unified perspective on the classical–quantum correspondence.

Conclusion

We have demonstrated that extended classical mechanics, when applied to stochastic non-inertial frames and subject to a variational stability principle, yields results matching key features of quantum mechanics. The Schrödinger equation, electron interference, and hydrogen spectrum emerge without quantum postulates.

This suggests that quantum theory may be a statistical approximation of deeper classical laws governed by stability and structure of the action in fluctuating frames.

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